

Studies on reduction of colour, COD and TSS in textile dyeing and printing wastewater by coagulation and adsorption method

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Abstract : Chemical coagulation and flocculation method was used for the laboratory scale investigations for the reduction in colour, COD and total suspended solids in textile dyeing and printing effluent. The COD, TSS and colour removal efficiencies can be obtained by appropriate combination of the aluminum penta hydroxyl chloride (coagulant) and clinoptilolite (flocculant), eversorb and bentonite as adsorbent. The results indicated that the COD, TSS and colour of the effluent can be reduced up to an extent of 65 to 70%. The trend of percent COD, TSS and colour reduction is fairly comparable to that of other chemical substances used by the treatment plants.

Keywords : Textile dyeing and printing wastewater, coagulation, adsorption, colour, COD, TSS reduction.

Introduction

Main pollution in textile dyeing and printing wastewater comes from kiering, mercerizing, dyeing and finishing processes. These processes require the inputs of a wide range of chemicals and dyestuffs, usually comprise of organic compounds of complex structure. Major pollutants in textile wastewaters are suspended solids, detergents, dyes, acids, alkalies, heat, colour, heavy metals and other soluble substances. Because all of them are not contained in final product as such becomes waste and causes disposal problems¹.

Environmental problems occur due to current practice of discharging untreated effluents into the stream. Strong colour of effluent is one of the greatest environmental problems. The presence of even small amount of dye in water (10–20 mg/L) is highly visible and esthetically undesirable. The dye affects the water transparency which in turn reduces photosynthesis activity in water bodies^{2,3}. Most of the chemicals present in effluents are non-degradable into nontoxic end products, so their concentration must be reduced to acceptable level before discharging them into environment.

Conventional treatments of wastewater containing organic compounds include biological oxidation, chemical

coagulation, advanced oxidation and adsorption. Biological methods are generally cheap and simple to apply and are currently used to remove organics and colour from textile dyeing and printing wastewater. However, this dyeing wastewater cannot be readily degraded by conventional biological processes e.g. the activated sludge process because the structures of most commercial dye compounds are generally very complex and many dyes are non-biodegradable due to their chemical nature, molecular size; thus, this results in sludge bulking. Although dyeing and printing wastewater can be effectively treated with wet oxidation, advanced chemical oxidation such as H₂O₂/UV, O₃ and adsorption using activated carbon, the costs of these methods are relatively high⁴⁻⁷.

Lime yielded a supernatant with a higher residual colour content, and the required dosage was 1.5–4 times as high as dosages for ferric sulphate and alum⁸. Coagulation prior to biological treatment might be advantageous for alkaline wastewaters⁹. Ferric chloride and sodium hydroxide removes 85–92% colour at pH 6.6–6.9. Alum was relatively more effective coagulant in colour removal¹⁰.

The control of water pollution by textile dyeing and printing wastewater is best achieved by a combination of

several in plant measures. The substitution of CMC, PVA, mineral acids and non-biodegradable detergents instead of starch, acetic acid and soap has reduced the BOD of the textile wastes. But the COD of the waste due to colour, total suspended solids and organic dyes is very high and the waste characteristics in respect of COD need to be reduced to satisfy the state water pollution control board's prescribed standards. Therefore, removal of colour, total suspended solids and COD from textile effluent is one of the important for environmental sustainability as these vital parameters determines how much a particular textile unit is eco-friendly.

In order to combat pollution, some experiments have been carried out as a part of the study for the reduction of COD, colour and total suspended solids from the effluent using chemical coagulation and flocculation.

Materials :

Aluminum is 100% recyclable without any loss of its natural quality. Recycling involves melting of the scrap, a process that requires only 5% of the energy used to produce aluminum from the ore. Recycle aluminum known as secondary aluminum maintains the same physical properties as primary aluminum.

Aluminum beverage cans were collected from local scrap market. They were cut into small equal pieces. These pieces were cleaned chemically and blocked to minimize oxidation losses when melted. Blocks were loaded into furnace and heated to 400 °C to produce molten aluminum. Dross formed was removed and dissolved hydrogen was degassed. The major components of aluminum powder waste are Al₂O₃-70%, SiO₂-11.2%, K and Na-15.6%, Fe₂O₃-2.7%, Ca, Mg and metals-0.5%. Coagulant i.e. aluminum penta hydroxyl chloride-Al₂(OH)₅Cl.6H₂O was prepared as : 50 ml of 20% solution of hydrochloric acid was introduced in the autoclave at 20 °C. After adding 50 g of aluminum powder waste the temperature was increased to 98 °C for 15 min. The admixture is filtered. The liquid phase was concentrated by evaporation at 160-170 °C. The final product was analyzed and determined as hydrated aluminum penta hydroxyl chloride. It is then mixed with the ground natural clinoptilolite as zeolite in the ratio of 100 : 1 to 100 : 5 by weight as flocculation agent.

Adsorbent eversorb is a grained, porous, activated carbon filter material with a very high ability of adsorption. It has large interior surface and wide adsorption

range for organic contamination, low tendency to clump, no release of silicic acid or heavy metals into the water, fully functional between pH 3 to 12 with higher retention capacity for solids. It was obtained from EVERS e.k water technology and filter materials.

Physical characteristics :

Grain size	0.8-2.2 mm
Effective grain size	0.9-1.1 mm
Moisture content	2.0%
Content of undersized particles	< 5%
Bulk density	450 kg/m ³
Iodine content (min)	1000 mg/L
Methylene blue content (min)	245 mg/g
Total surface according to BET	1050 m ² /g
Uniformity coefficient	1.4
Chlorine half-life length	2.8 cm

Bentonite is smectite group clay formed from the alteration of siliceous, glass-rich volcanic rocks such as tuffs and ash deposits. The major mineral in bentonite is montmorillonite, having hydrated sodium, calcium, magnesium and aluminum silicate. Sodium and calcium are interchangeable ions giving montmorillonite a ion exchange capacity. Bentonite has excellent rheological and adsorption properties. The composition of adsorbent eversorb depicts that it is predominantly carbonaceous in nature while bentonite is aluminosilicate. The eversorb and bentonite is used as adsorbent for effluent treatment in 1 : 1 ratio.

Results and discussion

The physico-chemical analysis of effluent (Table 1) reveals that textile effluent is highly polluted and com-

Table 1. Chemical character of effluent

Sl. no.	Chemical parameter	Effluent	Indian Standards for Industrial Discharge into Surface Waters (IS-2490; 1982)
1.	Electrical conductivity μ S/cm at 25 °C	10900	1000
2.	pH	10.4	5.5-9.5
3.	Temperature (°C)	45	40
4.	Colour (Visual)	Dark green	Colourless
5.	Total suspended solids (mg/L)	3250	100
6.	COD (mg/L)	1050	250

prises of typical strong odour due to the use of dyes and various inorganic and organic substances. The decay products contribute significantly to the foul smelling. The effluent is dark greenish in colour with high COD which is much higher than permissible limit for industrial effluents to be discharged into inland surface water. The results of coagulation studies are given in Table 2 and of adsorbent studies are given in Table 3.

and TSS is given in the Fig. 1. The results indicate that at pH 6, OD, COD and TSS reduction increases to a maximum of 37%, 29% and 51% respectively. After pH 6 the efficiency of coagulant decreases up to pH 9 i.e. reduction of OD, COD and TSS gradually decreases.

(ii) *Optimum contact time* :

It was evaluated by agitating 1000 ml sample at 200

Table 2. Effect of pH, contact time and coagulant dose on percent OD, COD and TSS reduction

(i) OD before treatment (λ_{max} 622 nm) : 0.429, (ii) COD before treatment : 1050 mg/L, (iii) TSS before treatment : 3250 mg/L

Sl. no.	pH	Residual			Contact time (min)	Residual			Coagulant dose (mg/L)	Residual		
		OD	COD (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)		OD	COD (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)		OD	COD (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)
1.	4	0.330	882	2047	30	0.343	924	2210	50	0.386	977	2145
2.	5	0.296	819	1788	45	0.326	893	1983	100	0.360	935	1983
3.	6	0.270	746	1593	60	0.742	851	1853	150	0.338	851	1853
4.	7	0.313	861	2048	75	0.291	798	1690	200	0.317	809	1723
5.	8	0.356	935	2503	90	0.270	746	1593	250	0.270	746	1593
6.	9	0.390	987	2795	105	0.270	746	1593	300	0.270	746	1593

Table 3. Effect of pH, contact time and adsorbent dose on percent OD, COD and TSS reduction

(i) OD before treatment (λ_{max} 622 nm) : 0.270, (ii) COD before treatment : 746 mg/L, (iii) TSS before treatment : 1593 mg/L

Sl. no.	pH	Residual			Contact time (min)	Residual			Adsorbent dose (g/100 ml)	Residual		
		OD	COD (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)		OD	COD (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)		OD	COD (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)
1.	4	0.113	343	828	30	0.176	440	1099	1.0	0.241	639	1019
2.	5	0.089	298	685	60	0.151	395	972	2.0	0.143	510	876
3.	6	0.068	238	558	90	0.122	358	828	3.0	0.102	427	685
4.	7	0.078	291	732	120	0.089	313	749	4.0	0.085	306	605
5.	8	0.097	320	844	180	0.078	276	637	5.0	0.068	238	558
6.	9	0.111	380	924	240	0.068	238	558	6.0	0.068	238	558
7.	-	-	-	-	300	0.068	238	558	-	-	-	-

Coagulation experiment :

(i) *Optimum pH* :

In order to evaluate the effect of pH, the experiments were performed by adding coagulant dose of 250 mg/1000 ml at 35 °C and agitating at 200 rpm for contact time of 300 min. The pH value of the effluent was varied from 4 to 9 using dilute NaOH or HCl solution. The various samples were agitated for optimum time after addition of the required coagulant dose. The solutions were filtered and analysed for residual OD, COD and TSS analysis.

The effect of pH on percent reduction of OD, COD

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on percent OD (◆), COD (■) and TSS (▲) reduction.

rpm with known amount of coagulant 250 mg/1000 ml for different time period of 30–105 min at the optimum pH 6.0 and temperature of 35 °C. After the selected time intervals the samples were filtered and residual OD, COD

and TSS were determined. Fig. 2 shows the percent reduction of OD, COD and TSS for different contact time of coagulant. The contact time was varied from 30 to 105 min and found that more than 27% OD, 19% COD and 43% TSS were removed within an hour. But afterwards the reduction occurred slowly and attained equilibrium in 240 min. The reduction in OD, COD and TSS was achieved to the extent of about 37%, 29% and 51% respectively by the coagulant.

Fig. 2. Effect of contact time on percent OD (◆), COD (■) and TSS (▲) reduction.

(iii) Optimum coagulant dose :

For the determination of optimum coagulant quantity, observations have been taken by varying the amount of coagulant at optimum pH. Effluent samples of (1000 ml each) were treated with different dose of coagulant varying from 50 to 300 mg/L. The experiment has been performed by maintaining temperature at 35 °C, contact time of 90 min, agitation rate of 200 rpm and pH of 6.0. The samples were agitated for minimum one hour duration and filtered. The effect of coagulant dose on percent reduction of OD, COD and TSS by aluminum penta hydroxy chloride and clinoptilolite is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Effect of coagulant dose on percent OD (◆), COD (■) and TSS (▲) reduction.

The maximum reduction took place at a coagulant dose of 250 mg/L in effluent sample. The colour (37%), TSS (51%) and COD (29%) were reduced to a considerable extent. The efficiency of OD, COD and TSS reduc-

tion by coagulation depends on solubility of organic contaminants. The organic contaminants with low solubility, such as dispersed dyes have been generally reported to be removed well by coagulation-flocculation methods. The organic contaminants with low solubility can be easily adsorbed and flocculated by coagulants but the soluble organic contaminants cannot be removed easily by coagulation.

Adsorption experiments :

(i) Optimum pH :

In order to evaluate the effect of pH on adsorption, the experiments were performed by adding adsorbent dose of 5 g/100 ml at 35 °C and agitating at 200 rpm for contact time of 300 min. The pH value of the effluent was varied from 4 to 9 using dilute NaOH or HCl solution. The various samples were agitated for optimum time after addition of the adsorbent dose. The solutions were filtered and analysed for residual OD, COD and TSS analysis.

The effect of pH on percent reduction of OD, COD and TSS is illustrated in the Fig. 4. The results indicate that at pH 6 the OD, COD and TSS reduction increases to a maximum of 75%, 68% and 65% respectively. But as the pH increases above 6 the efficiency of adsorbent decreases till pH 9 i.e. reduction of OD, COD and TSS gradually decreases. The reason for better adsorption capacity at pH 6 may be attributed to the presence of sufficient H^+ ions which neutralizes the negatively charged adsorbent surface, thereby reducing hindrances to the diffusion of ions at the optimum pH.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH percent OD (◆), COD (■) and TSS (▲) reduction.

(ii) Optimum contact time :

It was evaluated by agitating 100 ml sample at 200 rpm with known amount of adsorbent 5 g/100 ml for different time periods of 30 to 300 min at the optimum pH 6.0 and temperature 35 °C. After the selected time

intervals the samples were filtered and residual OD, COD and TSS were determined. Fig. 5 shows the percent reduction of OD, COD and TSS for different contact time of adsorbent.

Fig. 5. Effect of contact time on percent OD (◆), COD (■) and TSS (▲) reduction.

The contact time was varied from 30 to 300 min and found that more than 50% OD, COD and TSS were removed within an hour. But afterwards the reduction occurred slowly and attained equilibrium in 240 min. The reduction in OD, COD and TSS was achieved to the extent of about 75%, 68% and 65% respectively by the adsorbent. The smooth and independent nature of curve indicates formation of mono layer cover of the adsorbate on the outer surface of adsorbent.

(iii) *Optimum adsorbent dose :*

Optimum quantity of adsorbent dose was determined by keeping all optimum conditions with different adsorbent doses. For this 100 ml of effluents were agitated with calculated adsorbent doses of eversorb and bentonite mixture (1 : 1 ratio) for optimum contact time of 240 min. After filtration the samples were analysed for residual OD, COD and TSS. The experimental conditions were maintained by keeping temperature at 35 °C, agitation rate of 200 rpm and pH of 6.0 in all the samples.

The effect of adsorbent dose on percent reduction of OD, COD and TSS by eversorb and bentonite mixture (1 : 1) is shown in Fig. 6. It was found that maximum

Fig. 6. Effect of adsorbent dose on percent OD (◆), COD (■) and TSS (▲) reduction.

removal occurs at an adsorbent dose of 5 g/100 ml of effluent due to set up of equilibrium conditions. The results show appreciable reduction in colour (75%), TSS (65%) and COD (68%).

Conclusion :

The chemical characteristics of textile effluents show that these waters have high pollution potential in terms of inorganic and organic matter, so need to be treated before disposal. Certain pollutants like colour, TSS and COD in textile waste water are more important to target for pollution prevention than others. It is revealed from the study that the treatment of dyeing and printing waste waters can be done efficiently by using the appropriate combination of aluminum penta hydroxyl chloride and clinoptilolite, eversorb and bentonite to reduce the organic load. The COD, TSS and colour of the effluent can be reduced up to an extent of 65 to 70%. 72% COD removal efficiency is reported by electrocoagulation¹², 71% total COD, 76–92% colour removal was achieved with Al(SO₄)₃.18H₂O, FeCl₃ as coagulant¹³. The trend of percent COD, TSS and colour reduction is fairly comparable to that of other chemical substances used by the treatment plants.

Therefore, the best COD, TSS and colour removal efficiencies can be obtained by appropriate combination of the aluminum penta hydroxyl chloride and clinoptilolite, eversorb and bentonite. The treatment has also prevented eutrophication due to undesirable nutrients and bacteria and thus, the characteristics of wastewater were found to be within the standard limits for discharge.

Experimental

The combine textile dyeing and printing effluent was collected from industrial area and analysed for major chemical constituents. The batch mode was selected owing to its relative simplicity. The experiments were carried out on initial volume of 1000 ml of effluent samples. All the experiments were carried out at fix temperature in batch mode by varying the pH and doses of coagulant. The desired pH was maintained using dilute NaOH and HCl solution. Prior to each experiment a predetermined amount of coagulating + flocculating agent were added to samples for coagulation. The stirring was kept constant (200 rpm) for each run to maintain uniform mixing

throughout the experiment. After the predetermined time of one hour for coagulation, the treated effluent was filtered. To the filtrate, a predetermined amount of adsorbent was added to each sample and the process was accomplished under desired experimental conditions. Thereafter, the residual optical density (OD), chemical oxygen demand (COD) and suspended solids (TSS) of the filtered effluent sample were estimated as per standard APHA method¹¹.

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